

Kozlovska Iryna*PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Surgery №2 of Bukovinian State Medical University
Teatralna Sq., 2, Chernivtsi***Shkvarkovskyi Ihor***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Surgery №2 of Bukovinian State Medical University
Teatralna Sq., 2, Chernivtsi***Khorkholiuk Yuliia***Student of Bukovinian State Medical University Teatralna Sq., 2, Chernivtsi***Olenovych Olha***PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Clinical Immunology, Allergology and Endocrinology of
Bukovinian State Medical University Teatralna Sq., 2, Chernivtsi
Ukraine, 58002*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15011534>

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF TROPHIC ULCERS IN CHRONIC VENOUS INSUFFICIENCY

Abstract.

Chronic venous insufficiency of the lower extremities is extremely common in the modern world. It is defined as the presence of symptoms of venous stasis due to reverse blood flow in the veins (reflux) or narrowing or obstruction of the veins. Trophic ulcers are a serious complication of chronic venous insufficiency in the adult working population.

It has been established that trophic ulcers in the setting of varicose veins of the lower extremities occur in 1-3% of the population of industrialized countries. Trophic venous ulcers (TVU) account for more than 70% of all lower extremity ulcers. Their occurrence in the vast majority of observations (more than 55%) is due to varicose veins and only in 15% of cases - post-thrombophlebitic syndrome. Despite the existence of new treatments, the recurrence rate remains in the range of 20-70%. Therefore, for the effective treatment of trophic ulcers of venous etiology, it is necessary to clearly understand the etiology and pathogenesis of this pathology and to apply a comprehensive approach aimed at the known etiopathogenetic links in their treatment.

Key words: *trophic ulcer, chronic venous insufficiency.*

According to the WHO, venous disease of the lower extremities is diagnosed in 25% of the working population and more than 50% of people of retirement age in Europe. One of the most serious complications of chronic venous insufficiency (CVI) is trophic ulcers (TU), which are observed in approximately 2% of the world's adult population. They are the final stage of CVI and are the result of prolonged venous circulation disorders and a cascade of pathological changes in the microcirculatory bed and tissues of the lower extremities. Trophic changes of the skin and subcutaneous tissue in CVI usually develop in 7-12 years in women and 4-15 years in men. The etiopathogenesis of these ulcers is multifactorial and multicomponent. As a rule, such TVs do not heal for more than 6 weeks due to decompensation of the underlying disease [5].

There is no single interpretation of pathological changes in the veins of the lower extremities. This applies to both macrohemodynamics and microcirculation, and even more so to the variants and sequence of histochemical changes. Currently, the mechanisms that regulate trophic ulcers are a combination of macroscopic and microscopic pathological processes [1,4]. Macroscopic changes relate to pathological processes associated with the formation of varicose veins, the structure of the venous wall, and cellular abnormalities that impair venous function. These processes are primarily caused by genetic factors that lead to the destruction of the normal structure of the venous wall and the development of venous hypertension [1].

CVI is the main pathophysiological factor in the development of lower extremity DVT. One of the key mechanisms in the formation of these pathological changes is venous hypertension, which leads to impaired microcirculation, tissue hypoxia and chronic inflammation. The development of venous hypertension occurs as a result of venous system dysfunction, accompanied by impaired blood outflow [6]. The main causes of this condition are insufficiency of the valve apparatus of superficial, perforated and deep veins, which causes retrograde reflux, and this, in turn, leads to prolonged stagnation of blood and increased pressure in the venous bed. venous obstruction, for example, in post-thrombotic syndrome, also contributes to the development of venous hypertension, which impedes normal blood circulation. A decrease in the efficiency of the musculo-venous pump of the lower leg and foot due to physical inactivity, age-related changes or muscle weakness complicates the evacuation of venous blood and increases stagnation and venous hypertension [15].

Chronic venous stasis and increased capillary pressure cause a cascade of pathological changes in the microcirculatory bed, which worsens the course of CVI. Dilation of venules and capillaries due to increased venous pressure contributes to their deformation and increased vascular wall permeability [20]. An increase in endothelial permeability leads to the release of plasma, proteins, and other blood components into the interstitial space. This causes the development

of perivascular fibrosis, which impairs tissue metabolism. The progression of tissue edema disrupts the diffusion of oxygen and nutrients, creating conditions for hypoxia and dystrophic changes in the skin and subcutaneous tissue [8].

Impaired venous outflow in combination with venous stasis triggers pathological processes that eventually lead to the formation of trophic ulcers. Prolonged hypoxia and inflammation cause degenerative changes in the skin, and deterioration of reparative mechanisms does not allow the affected tissues to fully recover, which complicates ulcer healing. Thus, venous hypertension is a key factor in the pathogenesis of trophic ulcers, and its correction is an important component of the therapeutic approach to the treatment of chronic venous insufficiency [12,7].

Venous hypertension causes a chronic inflammatory reaction that can eventually lead to venous ulcers. The cause of inflammatory damage is chronic extravasation of macromolecules and red blood cell breakdown products, as well as iron overload. Chronic inflammation causes the extravasation of leukocytes into the dermis with the release of numerous pro-inflammatory cytokines [10]. These cytokines transform the phenotype of fibroblasts into a contractile phenotype, which increases tension in the dermis. In addition, iron overload leads to tissue destruction instead of dermal repair.

Veins are structurally and functionally different from arteries. Veins bring deoxygenated blood from the periphery to the heart and lungs, where reoxygenation occurs. The main structural difference between arteries and veins is the thickness of the vascular lining and the presence of valves. Thinner vein lining and better elasticity allows them to expand more and accumulate blood in the periphery. This venodilation creates vessels with low resistance, which provides easy forward flow. Blood moves through the veins mainly due to the contraction of the muscles of the upper and lower extremities, which act as a peripheral heart [3]. This is especially important for the lower extremities and is called the function of the calf muscles. The blood flow is maintained by a series of intraluminal valves. The main function of venous valves is to prevent reflux. When reflux or outflow obstruction occurs, venous hypertension develops [11]. In cases where it is high enough, ambulatory venous hypertension creates a chronic inflammatory environment. As a result of this chronic inflammation, microcirculation is disturbed. Clinically, this dysregulation is manifested by edema, skin fibrosis, degranulation of tissue basophils with subsequent itching, fibroblast differentiation into myofibroblasts, which leads to venous ulcers, and prolonged wound healing. Pain, tenderness, swelling, itching, hyperpigmentation, dermal fibrosis, and venous ulcers are clinical signs and symptoms that identify patients with CVI. Age, gender, pregnancy, weight, height, race, diet, bowel habits, occupation, posture, previous deep vein thrombosis, and genetic factors are considered predisposing factors for varicose veins [14, 19].

After the development of dynamic phlebohypertension and blood stasis as a result of endothelial dysfunction, which in turn leads to obstruction of the capillary lumen and aggregation of other blood cells. The resulting microthrombi lead to blockage of capillary blood flow and micronecrosis. The next stages in the formation of trophic disorders are precapillary shunting and systemic hemostatic disorders, which exacerbates microcirculatory stasis [18].

An important key mechanism for the development of DVT in CKD is microcirculatory disorders and tissue hypoxia. Prolonged venous stasis causes structural and functional changes in capillaries, which significantly impairs oxygenation and metabolic support of tissues. One of the important factors in this process is the formation of fibrin cuffs around the capillaries. Due to elevated venous pressure, fibrinogen circulating in the blood penetrates the endothelium and is deposited on the walls of microvessels [15]. This forms a kind of mechanical barrier that prevents the normal exchange of oxygen and nutrients between blood and tissues, causing progressive hypoxia and metabolic imbalance in cells.

An additional factor in tissue damage is red blood cell dyspepsis due to altered and weakened capillary walls. Penetrating into the intercellular space, red blood cells are destroyed, which leads to the release of hemosiderin, a form of iron that accumulates in tissues. An excess of hemosiderin provokes the development of oxidative stress, which is accompanied by damage to cell membranes, proteins, and DNA. This increases chronic inflammation and leads to further degeneration of the skin and subcutaneous tissue [17].

A significant contribution to the development of DVT is also made by the dysfunction of the endothelium, which normally performs a regulatory function, ensuring a balance between vasodilation and vasoconstriction. In CVI, endothelial cells are damaged, which leads to a decrease in the production of nitric oxide (NO), the main mediator responsible for vasodilation. As a result, persistent vasospasm occurs, which further disrupts microcirculation and increases tissue hypoxia. The combination of these pathological changes contributes to the development of degenerative processes in tissues, which subsequently leads to the formation of DVT [8, 17].

Chronic inflammation is another key pathogenetic factor in the development of ulcers in CVI. Under conditions of impaired venous outflow, leukocyte stagnation is observed in the microcirculatory bed, which leads to their activation and release of proinflammatory mediators, in particular interleukins (IL-1, IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α). These molecules trigger a cascade of inflammatory reactions that leads to tissue infiltration by neutrophils and macrophages. In turn, these immune cells exacerbate endothelial damage and destroy the extracellular matrix, which creates unfavorable conditions for tissue regeneration [1, 3].

An additional mechanism of damage is an imbalance between matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and their natural inhibitors (TIMPs). Patients with CVI have excessive MMP activity, which leads to the degradation of collagen and elastin, the main components

of the extracellular matrix. At the same time, TIMP deficiency does not allow compensating for this process, which contributes to further tissue destruction and makes normal wound healing impossible. Oxidative stress also plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of DVT. Free radicals cause lipid peroxidation, which destroys cell membranes and leads to cell death. In addition, reactive oxygen species cause DNA damage and mitochondrial dysfunction, which further slows down cellular regeneration and maintains chronic inflammation [20].

Against the background of a prolonged inflammatory process, degenerative changes occur in tissues, which further complicate reparative processes. Constant stimulation of the inflammatory response leads to the formation of replacement fibrosis and skin thickening, a condition known as lipodermatosclerosis. This reduces the elasticity of the skin, making it more vulnerable to injury and increasing the risk of ulcers.

Another critical factor is impaired angiogenesis, the process of forming new capillaries necessary for wound healing. Under normal conditions, vascular regeneration occurs due to the influence of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), but in chronic venous insufficiency, its level is significantly reduced. This inhibits the processes of vascular recovery, which increases tissue hypoxia and prolongs the healing time of trophic ulcers [2].

Thus, the combination of chronic inflammation, cellular dysfunction, fibrous changes, and impaired angiogenesis creates unfavorable conditions for tissue regeneration. The combination of these pathological processes not only contributes to the formation of DVT but also significantly complicates their healing.

The development of DVT is the final stage of the pathological processes that occur as a result of CVI. Due to prolonged hypoxia, inflammation, and oxidative stress, skin cells gradually lose their viability, which leads to necrotic changes. In conditions of insufficient oxygen and nutrients, epidermal and dermal structures are deeply damaged, resulting in their necrosis and the formation of an open ulcer [13].

In addition to ischemic and inflammatory tissue damage, a significant role in the chronicization of the ulcer process is played by a disturbance in the immune response. Weakened tissues create favorable conditions for the colonization of pathogenic microorganisms. Bacterial contamination serves as an additional factor in the formation of TV. At the same time, many authors emphasize that the microbial associations sown from the ulcer surface do not coincide with those obtained from areas of intact skin. Infection of the ulcer surface contributes to further tissue destruction, intensifies the inflammatory process and leads to the formation of purulent exudate. Chronic infection not only worsens the patient's condition, but also significantly complicates wound healing, as bacteria produce toxins and enzymes that disrupt normal repair processes [16].

Thus, a trophic ulcer is the result of a complex interaction of vascular, inflammatory, and infectious factors. Without appropriate treatment, the pathological process becomes chronic, which significantly reduces

the patient's quality of life and requires a comprehensive approach to therapy.

The etiopathogenesis of CVD and DVT is also considered taking into account genetic predisposition and modification of external risk factors. Genetic factors in combination with hormonal and mechanical triggers contribute to the formation of pathological venous reflux, which underlies the etiopathogenesis of trophic ulcers.

Varicose veins, which are often considered a hereditary disease, have impressive statistics confirming their genetic nature. Studies show that if both parents of a proband had varicose veins, the probability of its development in their offspring is 90%. At the same time, if only one of the parents had varicose veins, the risk of its occurrence in men reaches 25%, and in women - 62% [9]. This suggests the existence of an autosomal dominant type of inheritance with variable penetrance. However, the activation of this gene depends on a number of external factors. In women, the main triggers are estrogen, progesterone, and pregnancy, while in men, the development of varicose veins is often caused by heavy physical labor. This explains the earlier onset of the disease in women (C2) and its more severe course in men in later life (C3-C6) [17].

Given the pathogenesis of DVT, genetic predisposition to varicose veins and CVI creates conditions for the development of chronic venous stasis, venous hypertension, and microcirculatory disorders. Congenital weakness of the connective tissue, accompanied by dysfunction of the valvular apparatus of the veins, contributes to a gradual loss of venous tone, which leads to venous reflux, blood stasis, and tissue hypoxia. This triggers a cascade of pathological changes, including endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, oxidative stress, and microcirculatory disorders, which are key factors in the formation of trophic ulcers [5].

Hormonal factors, which play an important role in the development of varicose veins in women, also affect venous wall remodeling and angiogenesis. The imbalance between vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and proinflammatory cytokines contributes to the deterioration of reparative processes in tissues, which significantly complicates the healing of ulcerative defects. In men, the effects of physical activity and increased intra-abdominal pressure accelerate the development of venous stasis and exacerbate the manifestations of UC, which contributes to a later but more severe course of the disease [9,18].

The formation of venous ulcers requires macrovascular changes and the formation of varicose veins with reflux, followed by damage to the microcirculation and dermal structure. Pain in the lower extremities, edema, hyperpigmentation, lipodermatosclerosis and venous ulcers are the consequences of venous hypertension. One of the main reasons for the development and progression of varicose veins is the presence of pathological venous reflux, i.e. abnormal blood flow from the deep to the superficial (saphenous) vein system. At the same time, excessive blood volume (hypervolemia) and high blood pressure (hypertension) cause transformation of the saphenous venous network (dilation and pathological tortuosity), which is not adapted

to such actions and does not have strong skeletal structures in its own wall and surrounding tissues. As a rule, congenital or acquired degenerative-dystrophic changes in the valvular apparatus of the veins and their relative or absolute insufficiency are indicated as the cause of abnormal blood flow. Relative valve insufficiency means the absence of valve closure due to vein stretching and a relative lack of valve leaflet length. Absolute insufficiency is the absence of complete closure of the valves due to their organic damage (destruction, shortening) [4].

Veins have a single-cell endothelium, a middle layer containing smooth muscle cells (SMCs) separated by linear arrays of collagen bundles, and an adventitial layer of loose connective tissue. In normal veins, smooth muscle cells are spindle-shaped and separated by an organized layer of collagen. During the formation of varicose veins, the architecture of the media is severely disrupted. SMCs lose their contractile spindle shape and become rounded. Excessive and disorganized collagen deposition is observed between secretory smooth muscle cells, indicating a cause-and-effect relationship between dedifferentiation and varix formation [18].

The stages of venous trophic ulcers are key to understanding the development of the disease and choosing an effective treatment. The process of ulcer formation includes several stages characterized by different clinical manifestations:

1. Initial stage (skin changes)

Symptoms:

- Feeling of heaviness in the legs, especially after prolonged standing or walking.
- Swelling, which increases in the evening but disappears after rest.
- Skin color changes: hyperpigmentation (dark brown spots), especially in the ankle area.
- Reduced skin elasticity, the appearance of areas of compaction (lipodermatosclerosis).

Pathological processes: Venous stasis leads to microcirculation disorders, oxygen starvation of tissues and their damage.

2. Ulcer formation

Symptoms:

- The appearance of a small wound (usually in the area of the inner surface of the lower leg).
- An ulcer can begin with a minor skin injury (for example, due to a scratch) or a blister that does not heal.
- The skin around the wound is inflamed, red or with dark spots.
- Pain in the affected area, aggravated by movement or contact.

Features: The wound is irregularly shaped, shallow, with serous-purulent or bloody discharge.

3. Stage of ulcer progression

Symptoms:

- Increase in the size of the ulcer, it becomes deeper and affects the subcutaneous tissues.
- The ulcer may have necrotic areas.
- Increased pain, unpleasant odor due to infection.
- Systemic manifestations are possible: fever, weakness, intoxication.

Risks: If the infection spreads, it can lead to phlegmon, thrombophlebitis, or sepsis.

4. The healing stage

Symptoms:

- Reduced discharge, formation of granulations (pink areas of new tissue).
- Slow reduction in the size of the ulcer.
- Scar formation after complete healing.

Conditions for healing: Effective treatment, reduction of venous pressure, elimination of infection, proper wound care.

5. Remission stage (after healing)

- The ulcer closes, but a scar remains.
- The surrounding skin remains thin, vulnerable, with a risk of relapse.
- Without eliminating the underlying cause (venous insufficiency), ulcers may re-form.

Thus, the pathogenesis of trophic ulcers is a complex process involving the interaction of genetic, hormonal, mechanical, and vascular factors. The genetic predisposition to varicose veins, which often has an autosomal dominant type of inheritance, creates prerequisites for the development of CVI and venous stasis. This leads to impaired venous outflow, increased capillary pressure, and microcirculatory disorders, which in turn lead to the formation of DVT [2,19].

Hormonal changes, including estrogen, progesterone, and pregnancy in women, as well as physical activity in men, contribute to the activation of genetic factors and the development of varicose veins, which leads to the onset and chronicity of DVT. Chronic inflammation, cellular dysfunction, microcirculatory disorders, oxidative stress, and genetic triggers significantly impede healing, contributing to the development of persistent necrotic changes and infections.

Thus, for the effective treatment of TV, it is necessary to take into account not only the clinical manifestations of CVI, but also genetic, hormonal and external factors that affect the development and progression of this disease. An integrated approach to treatment, taking into account all these aspects, is the basis for improving the results of therapy and prevention in patients with DVT of venous etiology [5].

Conclusion. Trophic ulcers are usually a consequence of venous hypertension and chronic circulatory disorders, in particular venous insufficiency, which leads to tissue nutrition disorders and the formation of skin defects. However, the process of their development is complex and multifactorial, including not only vascular but also metabolic, infectious, and even immune aspects.

The formation of trophic ulcers in chronic venous insufficiency is the result of impaired venous outflow, which leads to stagnation of venous blood, increased venous pressure and the development of microcirculatory disorders. Chronic circulatory disorders in combination with inflammatory processes, insufficient tissue oxygenation and metabolic disorders lead to the formation of trophic ulcers that are difficult to treat. Prevention and early detection of chronic venous insufficiency are important components in preventing the development of trophic ulcers and improving the quality of life of patients.

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